

during final land preparation.

Regardless of method, 58 kg N/ha significantly improved panicles/m² and yield (see table). USG gave a grain yield advantage of 0.5 t/ha over PU. Differences among F, R, and M were

minimal.

Machine application increased yield 0.4-0.7 t/ha over broadcast split with PU at 58 kg N/ha. There was no difference between hand and machine

application methods with USG.

Placement of N fertilizer in the reduced zone as PU by machine or as USG by hand or machine gave higher agronomic efficiency. □

Effect of Zn and Cu on growth and nutrition of rice

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We studied the effect of soil application of Zn and Cu on dry matter yield and tissue concentration of Zn, Cu, Fe, Mn, and P in rice grown under submerged soil in a pot experiment in the greenhouse.

Soil was silty clay loam containing 20 ppm Olsen's P and DTPA extractable 0.64 ppm Zn, 0.46 ppm Cu, 11.6 ppm Fe, and 22.5 ppm Mn. Each pot contained 4.56 kg soil.

Basal nutrient application was 100 ppm N as urea, 26 ppm P as diammonium phosphate, and 25 ppm K as potassium chloride. Soil treatments were 0, 5, 10 and 20 ppm Zn and 0, 1, 2, and 5 ppm Cu as sulfates in a factorial combination with 2 replications.

Dry matter yield (g/pot)

Effect of Zn and Cu on dry matter yield of rice.

Effect of Zn and Cu on nutrient concentration in rice. ^a

Nutrient levels (ppm)	Nutrient concentration									
	µg/g tissue				mg/g tissue					
	Zn		Cu		Fe		Mn		P	
	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S	R
Zn 0	50.8	59.0	27.0	31.6	0.40	4.66	0.20	0.57	1.12	1.30
Zn 5	56.3	60.8	25.4	30.7	0.40	4.40	0.20	0.66	1.02	1.15
Zn 10	69.3	67.6	24.8	28.1	0.40	4.06	0.20	0.75	1.00	1.26
Zn 20	73.7	72.8	20.5	24.1	0.34	3.44	0.19	0.64	0.90	1.26
Cu 0	73.4	73.6	21.5	25.1	0.40	4.49	0.20	0.55	1.11	1.16
Cu 1	62.6	67.6	21.9	29.7	0.38	3.55	0.19	0.67	1.00	1.00
Cu 2	62.6	60.5	26.6	28.6	0.40	4.47	0.20	0.62	0.99	1.28
Cu 5	51.6	58.6	27.8	31.1	0.36	4.02	0.20	0.78	0.95	1.53
LSD (0.05)	5.4	1.8	1.9	1.9	0.02	0.25	0.01	0.06	0.02	0.04

^a S = shoots, R = roots.

Five 20-d-old IR8 seedlings were transplanted in each of 32 pots, thinned to 3 plants/pot, and grown for 72 d. Additional 20 ppm N as urea was applied 40 d after transplanting.

Highest increase in dry matter yield was from 10 ppm Zn + 2 ppm Cu (see figure). Application of 5 ppm Zn + 1 or 2 ppm Cu also increased yield. The highest rates of Zn (20 ppm) + Cu (5 ppm) failed to increase dry matter yield.

Zn in roots and shoots increased with Zn application but decreased with Cu

application (see table). Cu in roots and shoots increased with Cu application but decreased with Zn application of 10 ppm or more. Fe in roots decreased at all Zn levels and at 1 and 5 ppm Cu. Fe in shoots decreased with 20 ppm Zn and 1 and 5 ppm Cu. Mn in roots increased with Zn and Cu; in shoots, it decreased with 20 ppm Zn and 1 ppm Cu. P in shoots decreased with Zn and Cu. In roots, it decreased at all Zn levels and at 1 ppm Cu. Application of 2 and 5 ppm Cu increased P in roots. □

Biofertilizer production of stem-cut planted and seeded *Sesbania rostrata*

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Although *S. rostrata* is a promising green manure species for lowland rice farming systems, production of seed and scarification may be a problem for

farmers. Vegetative propagation appears attractive because nodulation sites constitute primordia of adventive roots able to grow under waterlogged conditions.

We compared biofertilizer production by vegetative propagation through stem cuttings (30 and 20 cm) and broadcast seeding, at 3 plant densities.

The experiment May-June 1988 at IRRI farm was laid out in a randomized split-plot design with four replications.

Influence of planting method and planting density on dry matter yield and some yield parameters of *S. rostrata* biofertilizer.^a

Treatment	Density	Plant height (cm)	Branches/plant (no.)	Dead plants/m ² (no.) ^b	Dry weight (t/ha)
<i>5-wk-old plants</i>					
Seeding	20 kg/ha	39 e	1 c	na	0.15 d
	40 kg/ha	41 e	1 c	na	0.41 bc
	80 kg/ha	37 e	1 c	na	0.55 bc
20-cm cutting	25/m ²	52 de	1.2 bc	3.2 bc	0.41 bc
	50/m ²	62 d	1.3 bc	7.1 ab	0.64 c
	100/m ²	76 c	1.3 bc	8.2 a	1.09 c
30-cm cutting	25/m ²	82 bc	1.9 a	1.2 c	0.89 c
	50/m ²	92 ab	1.5 b	2.6 c	2.31 b
	100/m ²	101 a	1.3 b	3.4 b	3.51 a
<i>7-wk-old plants</i>					
Seeding	20 kg/ha	85 e	1d	na	0.72 e
	40 kg/ha	87 de	1d	na	1.54 d
	80 kg/ha	104 d	1d	na	2.60 c
20-cm cutting	25/m ²	120 c	1.1 cd	2.9 bc	1.20 d
	50/m ²	125 c	1.2 c	6.2 ab	1.64 d
	100/m ²	146 b	1.4 b	8.3 a	3.48 bc
30-cm cutting	25/m ²	148 b	1.8 a	1.5 c	2.19 c
	50/m ²	165 a	1.3 b	2.5 c	4.31 b
	100/m ²	178 a	1.1 c	4.6 b	6.23 a

^a Duncan's multiple range test at 0.05. ^b na = data not available.

N accumulation in *S. rostrata*.

Plot size was 12 m². Stem cuttings of 8-wk-old plants were pushed about 5 cm deep into newly plowed and water-saturated soil (pH [KCl] 6.3, 1.1% organic C, 0.121% total N, 18.5 ppm P Olsen), 1.44 meq exchangeable K/100 mg CEC 33.9 meq/100 g). Plants were harvested at 5 and 7 wk.

Increasing planting rate resulted in increased biomass and N production. Cuttings showed faster growth and more dry matter and N production than seeds (see table and figure). Highest biomass and N yield were with 30-cm-long cuttings. They exhibited lower mortality and more branching than 20-cm-long

cuttings. To accumulate the same amount of N/ha, 30-cm-long cuttings require about 2 wk less growth than seeded plants. Only about 2-3 kg of seeds may be needed to produce enough plants for cuttings to plant 1 ha.

Broadcast seeding rate is 25-40 kg seeds/ha.

Although additional labor is needed to make and plant cuttings, it may be economical compared to seeding because it requires less seed, water management, and land preparation. Plants for cuttings might be grown on dikes and borders. □

Effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on ammonia volatilization loss in wetland soil

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Attempts are being made to identify short-duration leguminous green manure (LGM) crops that can be inserted into intensified cropping systems. High-yielding cultivars also leave large amounts of residue, which is either burned or incorporated into soil.

Crop residues and LGM may influence transformations of applied N. We studied the effect of sesbania green manure and wheat straw on ammonia volatilization from urea, in a laboratory study using the forced-draft chamber technique.

Ten pots (10 liters) containing 7 kg air-dry soil (pH 10.0, 0.35% organic C, 0.07% total N, and CEC 9.5 meq/100 g) were flooded, puddled, and preincubated with 1 cm standing water for 1 wk. Soil was then fertilized with 26 mg P/kg as single superphosphate and 50 mg K/kg as muriate of potash.

Treatments were N as urea alone or in combination with *Sesbania aculeata* green manure or wheat straw. N was applied at 100 and 200 kg N/ha. Finely chopped 2-mo-old fresh sesbania (2.5% N dry weight) was incorporated at